

FLOW BEHAVIOR OF ALUMINIUM- 15% BORON CARBIDE COMPOSITE BY DIFFERENTIAL STRAIN RATE COMPRESSION TEST

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Keywords: *Compression test, Aluminum, Boron carbide, Threshold stress, Hot rolling.*

Abstract

Compressive flow behavior of hot-rolled (64% reduction in thickness) Al and Al-15% B₄C composite was studied over the temperature and strain rate ranges of 25-500 °C and 10⁻⁴-1 s⁻¹, respectively, in longitudinal (LT) and transverse (TD) directions. It was found that athermal region (i.e. temperature-independent region) in aluminum becomes less prominent upon reinforcing with 15% B₄C particulates. The apparent stress exponent n' was found to vary between 10 to 30. It was also found that the stress exponent values could reduce to $n = 5$ upon subtracting the threshold stress from applied stress. Microstructural variation in aluminum was studied by EBSD and correlated with its flow behavior.

1. Introduction

Aluminum metal matrix-particulate composites (AMPCs) are attractive materials due to light weight, corrosion resistance and high strength. However, aluminum is commonly reinforced with ceramic particles such as SiC, AlN, SiN, and Al₂O₃ for strengthening [1-3]. Boron carbide (B₄C) is a promising covalently bonded ceramic material. It has many characteristics such as high hardness (Vickers hardness ~3.7 GPa), low density (~2.51 g/cm³), good thermal stability (melting point ~2700 K), along with high chemical and wear resistance. Aluminum- Boron Carbide (Al-B₄C) composites are recently developed metal matrix composite materials for the nuclear and armour applications [4-6].

Various aspects of Al-B₄C composites have been investigated in the literature. This includes study of fabrication and microstructures [7-9], chemical reactivity [10-11], wettability between Al and B₄C particles [12-16], workability [17] and strength enhancement by severe plastic deformation techniques [18-29]. However, only few reports are available in the literature on the flow properties at high temperatures [6,30-32]. Kai *et al.* [30] reported that weak interface leads to initiation of crack between matrix and particles in Al 7091-30% B₄C composite. Later, Onoro *et al.* [32] investigated tensile properties of Al 6061 and 7015 composites reinforced with B₄C particles over the temperature range of 25 to 500 °C, whereas Chen *et al.* [6] studied tensile properties of AA1100-B₄C composite over the temperature range of 25 to 300 °C.

To the best of our knowledge, no work is reported towards understanding the deformation behavior of Al-B₄C composite at elevated temperature. Therefore, the main objective of present work is to study the deformation behavior of hot rolled aluminum and Al-15 wt% B₄C composite and to examine the microstructural evolution towards exploring the structure–flow property correlation. Since rolled materials can exhibit anisotropy, current study aims to carry out deformation in both longitudinal (LT) and transverse (TD) directions. Samples in Longitudinal and Transverse directions hereafter are designated as LT and TD, respectively, unless otherwise stated. For comparison purpose, flow behavior of rolled commercial aluminum is also studied along with Al-15% B₄C composite.

Since most of the structural applications involve compressive loading [33], flow behavior of composites is evaluated by compression test instead of tensile test which generally shows poor ductility. Therefore, the present work is aimed towards investigating high temperature flow behavior of hot rolled aluminum and Al – 15 wt% B₄C composite in uniaxial compression. For this purpose, differential strain rate tests on hot rolled aluminum and Al-15wt% B₄C composite samples were conducted as a function of sample orientation i.e LT and TD over the temperature and strain rate ranges of 25 to 500 °C and 10⁻⁴ to 1 s⁻¹, respectively.

2. Experimental Procedure

A) Materials and Melting

Commercial aluminum of composition (wt%): Fe0.3-Si0.2-Mg0.1 and balance aluminum was used as matrix material. Boron carbide particles of average size 21 μm, obtained from boron carbide Ltd. India, were used as reinforcement. Al-15% B₄C composite was produced by flux assisted reaction method. Five kg aluminum of commercial purity was first melted in a crucible kept in a resistance pit furnace for about an hour. Potassium hexa fluoro titanate flux (K₂TiF₆), used for enhancing the wettability, was supplied by M. M. Enterprise, India. This flux was preheated at 300 °C for 3 hours and was mixed with B₄C particles prior to adding in liquid aluminum. The amount of flux was taken to be 10% of reinforcement content by weight. Five minutes after adding the flux to the molten aluminum and casting was done in a metal mould of size 20 × 20 × 600 mm³. These materials were subsequently hot rolled with their lengths parallel to the 600 mm length of ingot.

B) Hot Rolling

The produced ingots of Al and Al-15% B₄C were hot rolled at ~350 °C to total thickness reduction of 64% to 5mm final thickness, with intermittent annealing for 15 minutes at 400 °C after reductions of ~18, 34 and 49%. Compression testing samples of 5 mm diameter and 7.5 mm height were machined from both the longitudinal and transverse sections of the rolled plates. The rolling steps are given in Table I.

C) Compression Test

Differential strain rate compression tests were carried out with Zwick- Roell Amsler Universal Testing Machine of 100 kN capacity. The Strain rate sequence followed was: 1 × 10⁻⁴, 1 × 10⁻³, 1 × 10⁻², 1 × 10⁻¹ and 1 s⁻¹. Such tests on separate samples were done at temperatures ranging from 25 - 500 °C, viz 25, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 °C. Soaking time of 20 minutes was given after attaining the test temperature but prior to deformation. The test temperature was controlled within ± 2 °C in a three zone furnace. All samples were furnace quenched in liquid nitrogen upon completion of compression tests.

D) Metallographic Characterization

Morphology of boron carbide particles and the size distribution were characterized using Hitachi S-3400 model scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at 15 kV and particle size analyzer. The metallographic samples were mechanically polished with diamond paste of 1 μm size at the final stage. For Electron Backscattered Diffraction (EBSD), the samples were polished in an electrolyte of methanol and perchloric acid in the ratio 80:20 for 17 seconds at 13 volts. The EBSD was done to obtain micrograph and grain size on FEI Quanta-200HV SEM using a TSL-OIM (Tex. SEM Ltd.-Orientation Imaging Microscope).

3. Results and Discussion

The microstructural features of metal matrix composites i.e. grain size, subgrains and deformation field are difficult to reveal by conventional microscopy due to the surface roughness [9]. In this study, Electron Back Scattered Diffraction (EBSD) was used to understand the grain size variation and its effect on subsequent flow behavior of aluminum; in the case Al-15% B₄C composite, no such microstructural study could be done due to large wt% of reinforcement making it difficult. The initial microstructures of rolled aluminum in rolling and longitudinal planes are shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b) respectively. It is seen that the grains are elongated in rolling direction. It also reveals subgrains with

small variation in misorientation angle that develop from high angle regular grains by fragmentation.

A) Nature of stress-strain behavior

Figure 2 shows typical true stress- true strain curves for aluminum (Fig. 2a) and Al-15% B₄C (Fig. 2b) at room temperature, 300 °C and 500 °C. True stress-true strain curves at other test temperatures are not included in this figure for clarity. The flow stress increases with increase in strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon} = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, 1×10^{-3} , 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-1} and 1×10^0 s⁻¹) and decrease in temperature in both aluminum and Al-15% B₄C composite. Al-15% B₄C composite shows higher compressive strength than that of the aluminum. However, flow stress variation between the sample orientations LT and TD is insignificant at low (RT = 25 °C) and high (500 °C) temperatures in aluminum and Al-15% B₄C composite. In aluminum, the difference in flow stress between LT and TD at intermediate temperatures was found to be large. This variation might be due to microstructural variation in the two orientations during deformation.

B) Effect of Temperature

Figure 3 shows the plot of flow stress (normalized by Young's modulus) vs homologous temperature. The variation in modulus of aluminum [2] was taken according to Equation (1a) whereas the same for boron carbide was taken to be invariant as 460 GPa over the temperature range of interest, viz 25-500 °C [34]. Young's moduli of composites were estimated at corresponding temperatures using rule of mixture for the constituents (Al and B₄C) by Equation (1b). The flow stresses, at different temperatures, were normalized by moduli of the composite E_T at these temperatures [35].

$$E_{Al=matrix} = 85.09 - 0.049T \text{ GPa} \quad (1a)$$

where T = absolute temperature

$$E_{Composite} = E_{matrix} \times V_{matrix} + E_{particle} \times V_{particle} \quad (1b)$$

where, E_{matrix} , $E_{particle}$ and $E_{composite}$ are the Young's moduli of aluminum matrix, B₄C particle and Al-B₄C composite, respectively; V_{matrix} and $V_{particle}$ are the volume fractions of matrix and particle, respectively.

It is clear from Fig. 3 that the effect of reinforcement causes strengthening but there exists no effect on the nature of variation in flow stress as a function of temperature between Al-15% B₄C and aluminum (TD samples) over the entire temperature range investigated, except some anomaly of flow hardening in Al over 0.3 – 0.45 T_m . The absence of effect of temperature at lower temperatures may be due to athermal nature whereas the hardening effect with increasing temperature in aluminum may be dynamic strain aging. The Al-15 wt% B₄C composite shows higher strength at elevated temperatures due to B₄C particle reinforcement, which is common in dispersion hardened materials [3]. It is also seen that strain rate has greater effect on flow stress variation as a function of temperature in Al-15 wt% B₄C composite as compared to that in the aluminum. Normally, matrix grain size upon reinforcement decreases, which could lead to greater strain rate sensitivity in composite.

C) Stress exponent and Threshold stresses

Apparent stress exponent (n') was calculated, which relates the stress - strain rate behavior of Al-15% B₄C composite. Fig. 4(a) shows the nature of strain rate $\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\epsilon}\right)$ - stress (σ) plot in log-log scale at different temperatures following the constitutive equation (2) presented below.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \frac{DEb}{kT} \left(\frac{b}{d}\right)^p \left(\frac{\sigma}{E}\right)^{n'} \quad (2)$$

where A , b , σ , k , p , E and T are material and mechanism dependent constant, Burgers vector, flow stress, Boltzmann constant, grain size exponent, Young's modulus and absolute temperature, respectively. $D = D_0 \exp(-Q/RT)$ is diffusion coefficient with the terms having their usual meanings. The values of apparent stress exponent n'

is determined from the slope (Eq. 2) of curves in Fig 4(a). They vary from 10 to 30 depending on strain rate range and test temperature.

It is also clear that no effect of sample orientation on the magnitude of apparent stress exponent n' is noted at lower temperatures. However, n' value varies at higher temperatures. The high apparent stress exponent values were commonly attributed to the presence of threshold stress σ_{th} , which is shown to be inherent for all dispersion hardened materials [36, 37]. The true stress exponent n values are 3, 5 and 8 for dislocation glide, dislocation climb and invariant substructure model mechanisms, respectively [38]. These values of n are employed in estimation of threshold stresses σ_{th} according to the Lagneborg-Bergman plot i.e. (strain rate^{1/n} vs σ) [39], where it is the stress obtained by extrapolating the linear plot to strain rate of zero. In the present study, the stress – strain rate data are plotted as $\dot{\epsilon}^{1/n}$ vs σ by considering the n value of 5 as shown in Fig 4 (b), with best regression values above 90%. The value of $n = 5$ compares with that predicted by the dislocation climb controlled creep mechanism [40]. The magnitudes of threshold stress obtained are listed in Table II below. Therefore, in the constitutive relationship for high temperature deformation, the applied stress σ_a is substituted by effective stress ($\sigma^* = \sigma_a - \sigma_{th}$) as given below (Eq. 3).

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \frac{DEb}{kT} \left(\frac{b}{d} \right)^p \left(\frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_{th}}{E} \right)^n \quad (3)$$

The threshold stresses are noted to decrease with increase in test temperature as shown in Fig. 4 (b). It is also seen that the differences in threshold stresses between LT and TD samples at various temperatures are negligible. Doncel and Sherby [37] also reported similar results in 6061Al-20 vol% SiC_w composite.

4. Microstructural Evolution

The EBSD microstructures of aluminum (Fig. 1 and Fig. 5) show significant textural evolution during high temperature deformation. EBSD images of

aluminum deformed at room temperature show significant effect of sample orientation on texture component and grain structure, with the LT showing much finer grains than that in the TD orientation, Fig. 5 (a) and (b). Upon deformation at 500 °C, there appears distinct difference in the substructure evolved as shown in Fig. 5 (c) and (d). It is also noted that elongated grains changed into equiaxed grains at room temperature due to differential strain rate test, and further increase in grain size occurred as the test temperature increases. Such structural evolution is responsible for varying flow properties, although no structure could be delineated for the Al-15% B₄C composite. Figure 6 shows the plot of area fraction vs grain size of aluminum deformed at room temperature and 500 °C, in LT and TD directions. It is seen that no significant variation in grain size occurs between LT and TD samples, which is also clear from the similarity of flow curves (Fig. 2a). However, at intermediate temperatures (300 °C), the difference in flow behavior might be due to different extent of changes in microstructures between LT and TD samples towards similar state as the test temperature increases from 25 to 300 °C.

5. Conclusions

Differential strain rate compression tests of hot-rolled Al and Al-15% B₄C composite over the temperatures of 25-500 °C and the strain rate range from 10⁻⁴ to 1 s⁻¹ in longitudinal (LT) and transverse (TD) directions lead to the following conclusions:

- 1) The nature of flow stress variation as a function of strain between the LT and TD samples at lower and higher temperatures for the composite are found to be similar.
- 2) The rate of decrease in flow stress with increase in temperature (300-500 °C) arises from the contribution of high temperature flow mechanisms to deformation.
- 3) Stress exponent values are reduced to $n = 5$, from the apparent stress exponent n' values ranging from 10 to 30 by considering effective stress instead of applied stress.
- 4) The threshold stress in composite is found to decrease with increase in test temperature.

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However, no variation in threshold stress was found between LT and TD sample orientations.

- 5) EBSD microstructures of aluminum revealed the change in texture during the deformation over the temperature range of 25-500 °C.

6. Acknowledgement

We would like to thank Department of Science and Technology, India, for funding under FIST program SR / FST / ETII – 054 / 2000 for purchase of Universal Testing Machine. The authors also like to acknowledge OIM Texture Lab, IIT Bombay, for supporting the required work.

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Table I. Rolling schedule with cumulative % reduction in thickness followed in the present work

Material	1 st pass	Annealing for 15 minutes	2 nd pass	Annealing for 15 minutes	3 rd pass	Annealing for 15 minutes	4 th pass
Aluminum	18		33.5		49		63.5
Al+15% B ₄ C	18.11	34.15	49.4	63.7			

Fig. 1. EBSD Microstructures of aluminum in (a) Rolling and (b) Longitudinal planes.

Fig. 2. True stress vs true strain curves at room temperature, 300 °C and 500 °C of (a) aluminum and (b) Al-15% B₄C composite. (In all tests the $\dot{\epsilon}$ sequence followed are from LHS to RHS = 1×10^{-4} , 1×10^{-3} , 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-1} and $1 \times 10^0 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Fig. 3. Normalized flow stress (σ/E) as a function homologous temperature (T/T_m , T_m being melting point of aluminum matrix) for aluminum and Al-15% B₄C composite in TD.

Fig. 4. (a) Stress–Strain rate behavior and (b) replot of strain rate vs stress for determining threshold stress of Al-15% B₄C composite.

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Fig. 5. EBSD images of aluminum samples deformed in Rolling (a, c); Long transverse (b, d) planes at room (a, b) and 500 °C (c, d) temperatures.

Table II. Threshold stresses (MPa) obtained from Fig. 4(b) for Al-15% B₄C composite in longitudinal (LT) and Transverse (TD) directions at various test temperatures.

T, °C	500	400	300	200
LT	12.85	38.96	68.6	90.21
TD	20.1	54.19	75.45	90.56

Fig. 6. Grain size variation of aluminum samples deformed in LT, TD directions at room (a) and 500 °C (b) temperatures.